

Effect of Audio-script Assisted Instruction on Biology Students Achievements in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State.

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of Audio-script Assisted Instruction (AAI) on SS2 Biology students' achievements in Delta Central Senatorial District. The study adopted the quasi-experimental design using pre-test and posttest non-equivalent design. The population of the study comprised of 314 Biology students (141 males and 173 females), adopted from 4 intact classes. There was no sampling since the population size was manageable. Two research questions guided the study while, two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. Biology Achievement Test (BAT) was designed by the researcher and used as the instrument for data. The instrument (BAT) was face and content validated by three (3) experts, two (2) from the Department of Science Education and one (1) from Educational Measurement and Test Construction both of the Faculty of Education. Kudar-Richardson₂₀ was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument which yielded a reliability index of .78. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while, the t-test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses. The results of the study revealed that students in the experimental group achieved higher than those in the control group. Findings of the study further showed that male students achieved relatively higher than their female counterparts. However, sex has no statistically significant effect on the observed difference in students' achievements when taught Biology using AAI. It was therefore, recommended among others that secondary school Biology teachers and indeed, other science subject teachers should integrate and adopt AAI as an effective teaching strategy in secondary schools in Delta State.

Keywords: Audio-Script Assisted Instruction, Students' Achievements, Teaching Strategy and Biology

Introduction

The teaching and learning of science subjects have over the years been part of the Nigerian secondary education system. One of such science subjects is Biology. Biology is the study of living things; it is the science of life. Biology is taught at the secondary school level in order to provide students with a comprehensive grasp of biological ideas, theories, laws and principles. (Abidoye, Abidoye & Olaide, 2023, Bello et al., 2020). It includes the study of all living things, including ecosystems and the surface of the Earth, down to the smallest cellular components. Microbiology, biotechnology, genetics, botany, medicine, zoology, and bioinformatics are just a few of the branches of Biology. (Abidoye, Abidoye & Olaide, 2023).

The understanding of how the human body function is an important aspect of human existence. One of the subjects that gives opportunity to understand how the human body functions is Biology. Biology is a science subject studied at the senior secondary school level of Education. It deals with the understanding of how humans relate with the environment. It encompasses an in-depth inquiry into the natural world. The word Biology is coined from two Greek words ‘bios’ meaning ‘life’ and “logos” meaning “study”, with this, Biology is referred to as the study of life. Etim (2024), sees Biology as a study that aids in understanding the surrounding natural world. It can also be seen as the study of all living things. (Abidoeye, Abidoeye & Olaide, 2023).

One of the requirements that must be fulfilled before students who want to study science related courses will be given admission in the higher institution is that they must have a credit pass in Biology. An X-ray of the curriculum of Biology at the senior secondary school level revealed that the subject needs to be taught theoretically and through the use of practical activities. Literature have shown that the predominant method used in teaching Biology is the Lecture method (Thomas, 2021).

Lecture method is a teacher-centered method that gives students little room for participation during the teaching and learning process. Ajaja (2009) sees Lecture method as the talk-chalk approach. The lecture method is the type of teaching approach where the teacher delivers information to students through oral presentation, often with minimal student participation. However, it’s often beneficial to combine lectures with other teaching strategies and methods like discussion, group work, practical activities, use of audio-visual aids etc to create a more engaging and interactive learning environment (Suhaimi, Khalid & Asma, 2020). One of such instructional strategy is Audio-script Assisted Instructional Strategy.

As a result of introduction of technology into education, another method that can be combined with Lecture Method and emphasizes the use of ICT device is Audio-Script Assisted Instruction (AAI), also known as Audio-script Assisted Instructional strategy. Audio-script Assisted Instructional strategy is a strategy that involves the use of audio recorded script in teaching. In using this strategy, students are made to listen to the recordings several times.

According to Abubakar (2001) audio and compact disc training has a lot of promise for use in teaching and learning environments. The simplest way for students to develop receptive skills is to listen to a wide range of topics in a variety of genres, dialogues, interviews, and lectures. Additionally, audiotape is the most widely available voice recording device and may be utilized to meet learning objectives in the cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor domains of learning which helps to enhance student’s motivation (Nworgu, 2000). It is believed that when appropriate methods are used in teaching and learning, there would be improvement in students’ academic achievements.

Academic achievement in Biology refers to students’ performance abilities in Biology. Academic achievement, according to Akpan (2012), is the extent of a student's performance or attainment in the academic or curricular subject that they are required to learn in the classroom. Academic achievement, according to Ebun (2013), is the overall performance of students in all subject areas and is influenced by a wide range of circumstances. The answer a student gives to standardized scholastic aptitude exams is a measure of their academic achievement in nations such as Nigeria, where many forms of standardized testing are used. The degree of response on these tests may be used to determine a student's success. Evidence that is now available shows that biology student success has been quite disappointing at the secondary school level.

This scenario is especially depressing when we consider the fact that adequate knowledge of Biology is a prerequisite for our country's scientific and technological progress. The biology students' low performance on the certificate exams is the result of a multitude of issues relating to their cognitive and motor abilities. How to persuade scientific instructors to adopt a new strategy instead of sticking with the conventional method of teaching science has been a source of worry (Suraj, Yusuf, Bukar, Tijjani & Ibrahim, 2021, Judith et al, 2014)). One of the main reasons why students do poorly in biology classes in Nigerian secondary education is due to teachers' inadequate utilization of the instructional aids they have adopted (Suraj, Yusuf, Bukar, Tijjani & Ibrahim, 2021). When teachers utilize appropriate instructional aids, students may exhibit good and outstanding academic grades irrespective of their sex.

Sex is defined as the biological traits that make a person male or female. Sex is one of the variables that may be taken into account in Biology (Griffiths, 2021). Since Biology classroom is made up of male and female students who intend to further their educational career in science related courses at the higher institutions of learning. According to Johnson et al, (2007), when appropriate teaching methods are used in teaching, students' academic achievements are more likely to improve irrespective of their sexes.

From the forgoing, it could be seen that the Audio-script Assisted Instructional strategy is different in terms of content presentation. It is against this backdrop therefore, that this study was aimed to determine the effect of AAI teaching strategy on SS2 Biology students' achievements in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State.

Statement of the Problem

Biology, as an important science subject, provides students with the foundational knowledge necessary for careers in medicine, agriculture, pharmacy, and other life sciences. However, despite its importance, students' achievement in Biology in Nigerian secondary schools, particularly in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State, has been reported low (Bichi et al, 2029). This poor achievement is evident in students' performance in external examinations such as the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and the National Examination Council (NECO). Several factors have been attributed to this trend, including ineffective teaching methods, lack of adequate instructional materials, and students' poor study habits.

One of the major concerns in the teaching of Biology is the continued reliance on conventional lecture-based methods that emphasize rote memorization, leading to poor retention and low academic achievement (Statistical Analysis on Influence of Biology Laboratory Practical on Senior Secondary Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin East LGA, Kwara State, 2023). In contrast, innovative instructional strategies, such as Audio-script Assisted Instruction, have been proposed as potential solutions to enhance students' achievements in Biology.

Despite the potential benefits of Audio-script Assisted Instruction, its effectiveness in improving Biology students' achievements in Delta Central Senatorial District remains largely under-explored. Moreover, the extent to which this instructional strategy can bridge the learning gaps caused by traditional teaching methods has not been sufficiently examined. Given that students in Delta Central Senatorial District come from diverse socio-economic backgrounds with varying levels of access to educational resources, it becomes imperative to examine whether Audio-script Assisted Instruction can serve as an effective intervention to improve learning outcomes in Biology.

Additionally, sex differences in science achievement have been widely documented in educational research, raising concerns about whether instructional strategies such as Audio-script Assisted Instruction benefit male and female students equally. While some studies suggested that sex disparities in science achievement may be linked to differences in learning preferences and engagement levels (Ngbarabara, 2023), there is a need for further investigation into how audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy influences male and female students differently.

Given the persistent poor performance of Biology students, the limitations of traditional teaching methods, and the potential of audio-script assisted instruction as an alternative pedagogical approach, it is imperative to conduct an empirical study to examine its effects on students' achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State. This study provided evidence-based recommendations for teachers, policymakers, and curriculum developers on the adoption of innovative strategies to improve Biology education in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the effect of Audio-script Assisted Instruction on SS2 Biology Students' Achievements in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State.

In specific terms, the study was intended to determine the:

1. Mean achievement scores and standard deviation of students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method in both pre-test and posttest.
2. Mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method in both pre-test and posttest.

Research Questions

The following two (2) research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method in both pre-test and posttest?
2. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method in both pre-test and posttest?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using Lecture method (Control Group) in both pre-test and posttest.
2. There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy (Experimental Group) in both pre-test and posttest.

Methodology

The study focused on effect of Audio-Assisted Instructional teaching strategy on SS2 Biology students' achievements in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State. Two research questions guided the study. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested of .05 level of significance. The quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. The study population comprised of 314 Biology students from 4 intact classes. There was no sampling since the population size was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a 20-item Biology Achievement Test (BAT), developed by the researcher and validated by three (3) experts in Biology Education and Educational Measurement and Test Construction. The instrument reliability was ascertained using the Kuder-Richardson₂₀ formula which yielded a reliability index of .78. The data relating to the research questions were analysed using mean and standard deviation while, the t-test statistics was used to test the stated null hypotheses. The decision rule regarding the research questions was; reject the null (H₀) if the significance of F-Critical value is less than .05, otherwise, do not reject.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method in both pre-test and posttest?

Table 1.1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations Taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional Strategy and those Taught using Lecture Method in both Pretest and Posttest.

Groups	Testing	N	X	XDiff	SD
LM	Pretest	200	35.56	22.98	9.69
	Posttest		58.54		12.67
AAI	Pretest	114	16.60	23.66	6.59
	Posttest		40.26		5.17

Table 1.1 shows the mean achievement scores of students taught with Lecture method (LM) and Audio-script Assisted Instruction (AAI) at both pretest and posttest. For the lecture group, the students mean achievement score at pretest was 32.56 with a Standard deviation (SD) of 9.69 while, at posttest they had a mean achievement score of 58.54 with a standard deviation of 12.67, there is a mean difference of 22.98 in favour of their posttest scores. The table shows also that for the AAI group, the students had a mean achievement score of 16.57 with a standard deviation score of 6.59 at pretest and at posttest, they had a mean achievement score of 40.26 with a standard deviation score of 5.17 from the mean scores, it could be seen therefore, that the students mean at posttest is higher with a mean difference of 23.66 in favour of their posttest score. To determine if these differences are significant, the paired sample t-test statistics was used to test H₀₁.

H0₁: There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using Lecture method (Control Group) in both pre-test and posttest.

Table 1.2: There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using Lecture method (Control Group) in both pre-test and posttest.

Groups	Testing	N	X	XDiff	SD	Df	tcal	Sig. 2 tailed
LM	Pretest	200	35.56	22.98	9.69	199	11.98	0.00
	Posttest		58.54		12.67			
A-SI	Pretest	114	16.60	23.66	6.59	113	4.36	0.00
	Posttest		40.26		5.17			
	Posttest		62.86		10.28			

Table 1.2 shows that the observed difference in table 1.1 is significant since the calculated sig-value of 0.00 which is less than 0.05 alpha level of significance that was obtained. With this, H0₁ which states that ‘There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using Lecture method (Control Group) in both pre-test and posttest’ is rejected.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method in both pre-test and posttest?

Table 1.3: There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method in both pre-test and posttest.

Groups	SEX	N	X	XDiff	SD
LM	Male	200	59.91	2.31	14.86
	female		57.60		10.90
AAI	Male	114	40.67	0.86	4.46
	female		39.81		5.88

The Table 1.3 shows the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Biology with LM and AAI in the experimental group. For the AAI group, the males had a mean of 40.67

with a standard deviation of 4.46 while the females had a mean of 39.81 with a standard deviation of 5.88 both with a mean difference of 0.86 in favour of the males. For the LM group, the males had a mean of 59.91 with a standard deviation of 14.86 while the females had a mean of 57.60 with a standard deviation of 10.90 both with a mean difference of 2.31 in favour of the males also. This implies that the AAI teaching strategy is a gender responsive pedagogy. To determine if these differences are statistically significant, the paired sample t-test was used to test H_{02} .

H_{02} : There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method in both pre-test and posttest.

Table 4: There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy (Experimental group) in both pre-test and posttest.

Groups	N	X	XDiff	SD	tcal	df	Sig(2 tailed)
Male	54	40.67	0.86	4.46	0.877	112	0.383
Female	60	39.81		5.88			

Table 1.4 above shows that the observed difference is not statistically significant since the sig. values of 0.383 for the experimental group is greater than 0.05. Therefore, H_{02} which states that ‘There is no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional strategy (Experimental group) in both pre-test and posttest’ is not rejected.

Summary of Findings

Results of the analyses of data presented above showed that: 1. Biology Students’ achievements improved, especially those in the experimental group. It therefore, means that, SS2 students benefited from the teaching of Biology when taught using the AAI strategy than the control group. 2. The male students achieved relatively higher than their female counterparts. However, there was no statistically significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students in the experimental group.

Discussion

Students’ Mean Achievements Scores When Taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional Strategy

The findings revealed that students taught Biology using audio-script assisted instruction had higher achievement scores than those taught using the lecture method. This implies that employing audio-script assisted instruction is effective in enhancing students’ academic achievement in Biology, proving that this instructional approach serves as an effective pedagogy for improving students’ learning outcomes. This finding aligns with Miezah & Whajah (2023), who conducted a survey on the effect of using videos in Biology lessons on students’ performance. Their study showed that the experimental group (Video and Audio) outperformed the control group (lecture

class) in post-test performance, indicating the effectiveness of innovative instructional strategies in improving students' learning outcomes.

Similarly, Oruakpor and Oyovwi (2024) supported the findings of this study, revealing that Computer Audio Assisted Instruction enhanced academic success and increased students' learning achievements in Biology. Additionally, Nwuba and Osuafor (2023) found that students instructed using crossover and voice-over instructional strategy scored higher on both the post-test and delayed post-test compared to those taught using the lecture method, further reinforcing the effectiveness of alternative teaching strategies. This serves as clear evidence that audio-script assisted instruction is highly effective in enhancing students' academic achievement in Biology.

Male and Female Students' Achievement Scores when Taught Biology using Audio-Script Assisted Instructional Strategy

The study revealed that male students had higher achievement scores than their female counterparts when taught Biology using audio-script assisted instruction. This implies that male students benefited more from the use of audio-script assisted instruction than female students. Therefore, audio-script assisted instruction is an effective strategy for improving students' academic achievement in Biology.

Further findings indicated no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Biology using audio-script assisted instruction. This finding is consistent with the study by Umeh, Nsofor, Oboh, and Idris (2013), which found no significant difference in the achievement scores of male and female students. It also agrees with the findings of Adigun, Onihunwa, Irunokhai, Sada, and Adesina (2011), which revealed that male students had slightly better achievement scores than female students, though the difference was not significant. The findings of this study suggests that audio-script assisted instructional strategy is an effective teaching strategy for improving Biology students' academic achievement.

Conclusion

The study revealed that audio-script assisted instruction is an effective method for improving students' academic achievement in Biology. The study showed that students taught using audio-script assisted instruction had higher achievement scores than those taught using the expository method. Therefore, audio-script assisted instruction is an effective pedagogy for enhancing students' academic achievement among both male and female students. However, there is no statistically significant difference in the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students, even as male students were seen to have achieved better than their female counterparts. The study, therefore, concluded that audio-script assisted instruction should be introduced in all public secondary schools, as it is an effective teaching strategy that enhances learning outcomes in Biology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following two recommendations were made:

1. When teaching Biology concepts in senior secondary schools, Biology teachers should be encouraged to use the Audio-script Assisted Instructional strategy.
2. Biology Teachers should be trained through workshop and seminars to equip them with the necessary skills needed for the usage of Audio-script Assisted instruction.

References

- Abidoye, F. O, Abidoye, A. A & Olaide, M. S (2023). The Effect of Biology Teaching Materials on the Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Ilorin West, Ilorin, Kwara State. *International Journal of Educational Innovation and Research*. 2(2), 142-150.
- Abubakar, M. M. (2001). The impact of information technology on the Biological Science. *Journal of Science Education*, 5(1&2), 16-20.
- Achebe, A. E. (2008). Effect of videotape instructional package on achievement and retention in food and nutrition at senior secondary school level in Minna, Niger State. *JOSTMED*, 1(1), 33-39.
- Adamu, A. (2007). *Effect of tape-recorder on learning of oral English in secondary schools in Minna, Niger State*. Unpublished M.Tech. thesis, Department of Science Education Federal University of Technology, Minna. Nigeria.
- Adegoke, B. A. (2010). Integrating animations, narrations and textual materials for improving students' learning outcomes in senior secondary school physics. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 8(2), 725-748.
- Adigun, J., Onihunwa, J., Ironokhai, E., Sada, Y. & Adesina, O. (2011). Effect of Gender on Students' Academic Performance in Computer Studies in Secondary Schools in New Bussa, Borgu Local Government of Niger State. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(33), 1-7.
- Akpan, P. S. (2012). Effect of reduced readability text materials on comprehension and chemistry achievement. *Journal of Science Education*, 68(2), 24-36.
- Baumeister, R.F. & Vohs, K.D. (2007) Self-Regulation, Ego Depletion, and Motivation. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 1, 1-14.
- Bello, G., Alabi, H. I., Ahmed, A. R., Sulaiman, M. M. S., Bello, Z. A. B., & Bello, A. A. B. (2020). Biology education and bio entrepreneur opportunities in Nigeria. *Nigerian Online Journal of Educational Sciences and Technology*, 1(2), 1-17.
- Bichi, A. A., Ibrahim, R. H., & Ibrahim, F. B. (2019). Assessment of Students Performances in Biology: Implication for Measurements and Evaluation of Learning. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 13(3), 301-308. <https://doi.org/10.11591/EDULEARN.V13I3.12200>
- Bishop, M. J. & Cates, W. M., (2001a). A framework for researching sound's use in multimedia instruction to enhance learning, *Paper presented at American Educational Research Association, Seattle, WA*, (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 453 243)
- Cimer, A. (2012). What makes biology learning difficult and effective: Students' views. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 7(3), 61.
- Clark, R., Mayer, R., & Thalheimer, W. (2003). E-Learning and the Science of Instruction: Proven Guidelines for Consumers and Designers of Multimedia Learning. *Performance Improvement*. 42. 41-43.
- Ebun, C.E (2013). The readability of managerial accounting and financial management textbooks. *Meditar Accounting Research*, 19(2), 102-112
- Griffiths, P. E. (2021). *What are biological sexes*. <http://philsci-archive.pitt.edu/19906/>
- Thomas, C. G. (2021). *Guidelines for Successful Lecturing* (pp. 523-541). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64865-7_21

- Miezah, W. S., & Whajah, G. (2023). A Survey on The Effects of Using Videos in Biology Lessons on Student Performance. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, 118–132. <https://doi.org/10.32628/ijrst5231047>
- Ngbarabara, P.B. (2023). Effects of Computer Game-Based Teaching Strategy on Junior Secondary Schools Computer Studies Students' Retention Abilities and Gender in Rivers State. *Shodh Sari-An International Multidisciplinary Journal*, 02(02), 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.59231/SARI7578>
- Nworgu, B. G. (2000). Improving the teaching and learning of introductory technology through the use media. *Journal science Teacher Association of Nigeria* 7 (28), 18-19.
- Nwuba, I., & Osuafor, A. M. (2023). Examining of crossover instructional strategy toward biology students' academic performance in secondary schools. *Inornatus*, 3(2), 50–59. <https://doi.org/10.30862/inornatus.v3i2.420>
- Oruakpor, J. A., & Oyovwi, E. O. (2024). Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) With Animation in Biology Curriculum Delivery: A Panacea for Students Achievement and Motivation. *British Journal of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bje.2013/vol12n55870>
- Statistical Analysis on Influence of Biology Laboratory Practicalon Senior Secondary Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin East Lga, Kwara State.* (2023). 1(3), 229–238. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijsmr.v1i3.3395>
- Suraj, J.M, Yusuf, M. S., Bukar, G., Mohammed, T. & Ibrahim, A.M. (2021). The impact of instructional aids on academic achievement of biology students in higher institutions of learning in Potiskum Local Government Area, Yobe State. *GSC Advanced Research and Reviews*, 09(01), 172–178
- Umeh, A. E. O., Nsofor, C. C., Oboh, C. O. & Idris, U. S. B. (2013). Computer Game Assisted Instruction and Students' Achievement in Social Studies; *Journal of Research in National Development* [www.transcampus](http://www.transcampus.org) (JORIND) 11(1), www.transcampus.org/journals; www.ajol.info/journals/jorind.